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Correction: Chitosan-gated organic transistors printed on ethyl cellulose as a versatile platform for edible electronics and bioelectronics

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Correction for 'Chitosan-gated organic transistors printed on ethyl cellulose as a versatile platform for edible electronics and bioelectronics' by Alina S. Sharova *et al.*, *Nanoscale*, 2023, **15**, 10808–10819, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D3NR01051A>.

The authors regret that in the original article the weight of semiconductors present for each inverter was erroneously reported, due to a calculation error. Table 1 indicated a “Dose per device” of 4 pg for both P3HT and P(NDI-C4-TEGMe-T2), however, the correct doses are 8.4 ng for P3HT and 16 ng for P(NDI-C4-TEGMe-T2). The authors confirm that the main findings and conclusions of the work are not affected by this error. While the actual dose of semiconductors per inverter is three orders of magnitude greater than what erroneously reported in the original manuscript, such a value still represents a very small trace with respect to the total volume of the device, *i.e.*, nanograms *vs.* milligrams.

The correct Table 1 is reported below:

Table 1 Estimated amounts of materials constituting a single inverter based on chitosan-gated transistors in grams per device, with the corresponding reported daily intake and FDA *E* value

Material	Dose per device	Allowed daily intake
P3HT	8.4 ng	N.A.
P(NDI-C4-TEGMe-T2)	16 ng	N.A.
Ethylcellulose	~3 mg	660–900 mg kg ⁻¹ day ⁻¹ (E462)
Printed gold	2 μg	N.A. (1.32 μg kg ⁻¹ day ⁻¹ for E175 edible gold)
Printed silver	10 μg	N.A. (12 μg kg ⁻¹ day ⁻¹ for E174 edible silver)
Chitosan	0.2 mg	6 g day ⁻¹
Glycerol	0.04 mg	2 g kg ⁻¹ day ⁻¹ (E422)

In addition:

- In the abstract: “including biocompatible polymers present in the picogram range per device” should be: “including biocompatible polymers present in the nanogram range per device”.
- On page 10816, left column, line 24: “range of picograms per device” should be: “range of nanograms per device”.
- On page 10816, right column, line 21: “*i.e.* picograms per transistor” should be: “*i.e.* nanograms per transistor”.

The Royal Society of Chemistry apologises for these errors and any consequent inconvenience to authors and readers.

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